

VIRGINIA DATA CENTER RESEARCH & INDUSTRY DIRECTORY

A Multi-Disciplinary Expert, Resource & Contact Guide

Prepared for the Emory University / Alfred P. Sloan Foundation Data Center Project

Version 3.0 — June 2026

Contacts verified June 2026

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What's New in v3.0

Version 3.0 incorporates three months of portfolio work since v2.1 (March 22, 2026) and a full June 2026 re-verification of every entry. Every existing Part I and Part II contact received a link-rot and still-in-role check; the changes were substantial — Mark Christie left FERC for William & Mary, Will Cleveland left SELC, Henrico's EDA changed directors, QTS promoted its government affairs lead to co-CEO, and Mecklenburg Electric has a new CEO. Part II gains the developers, utilities, economic development bodies, and community coalitions surfaced by the Hanover, Chesterfield, Goochland, Botetourt, Mecklenburg, Louisa, Culpeper, Orange, and Prince William case studies, including Tract, EdgeCore, WestDulles Properties, LS Power, Commonwealth Fusion Systems, Appalachian Power, the Western Virginia Water Authority, and the Hitachi Energy South Boston transformer plant. Part III adds the 2026 NVTC report (now produced by Mangum Economics, not Weldon Cooper), the GMU home-sales study, Data Center Watch, MultiState's legislation tracking, the primary SCC dockets (GS-5, CERC, and both IRP cases), and the series' own published case studies with DOIs. Part IV is new: a region-by-region guide to local press and beat reporters for October 2026 fieldwork, with outlet status and bylines verified against the 2025–2026 record. Where a direct contact could not be confirmed against the organization's current site, the entry lists the verified institutional channel and is marked [general channel only].

How to Use This Directory

This directory consolidates researchers, institutional resources, advocacy organizations, trade associations, industry contacts, and local press relevant to the multi-disciplinary study of data center impacts in the United States. It is designed as a working outreach tool for the Emory/Sloan three-year research project and for anyone conducting serious policy or academic work on the data center buildout.

The directory is organized in four major parts:

Part I: Researchers & Experts organized by discipline, with standardized entries including position, institution, research focus, verified contact links, and key publications with direct URLs.

Part II: Virginia Industry Contacts covering trade associations, hyperscale operators, colocation providers and campus developers, utilities and cooperatives, local economic development authorities, the supply chain, and advocacy coalitions, with named contacts where published.

Part III: Key Reports & Data Sources providing a consolidated reference list of essential institutional reports, primary regulatory dockets, and tracking sources.

Part IV: Local Press & Beat Reporters organized by region, listing the outlets and reporters whose bylines carry the Virginia data center record — the primary entry points for fieldwork in October 2026.

Note on contact information: Direct email addresses and phone numbers are included only where they appear on the organization's current website, in published directories, or in the organization's own press materials, re-verified June 2026. Entries marked **[general channel only]** mean no direct contact could be verified; use the institutional channel listed. Contacts carried over from v2.1 that could not be re-confirmed are marked **[not re-verified June 2026]**. No contact in this directory is inferred or guessed.

PART I: RESEARCHERS & EXPERTS

1. Regional Economics & Fiscal Policy

Terance (Terry) J. Rephann, Ph.D.

Position: Regional Economist

Institution: Weldon Cooper Center for Public Service, University of Virginia

Discipline: Regional Economics; Public Finance

DC Research Focus: Fiscal impact of data centers on Virginia localities; the \$26-to-\$1 tax-to-services ratio in Loudoun County; job density analysis (25 direct + 25 contract employees per 250,000 sq ft facility); LULU (Locally Unwanted Land Use) research; Great Lakes regional data center economic impacts (Joyce Foundation)

Contact & Links:

Institutional Profile: <https://www.coopercenter.org/team/terry-rephann>

Key Publications / Reports:

Economic, Fiscal and Energy-related Impacts of Data Centers in the Great Lakes Region (2026). Weldon Cooper / Joyce Foundation (with Ferreira, Shobe & Scheffel)

<https://www.coopercenter.org/research/GLDC>

The Impact of Data Centers on Virginia's State and Local Economies (2024). NVTC / Weldon Cooper

<https://loudounpossible.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/2024-NVTC-Data-Center-Report.pdf>

Joao Pedro Ferreira, Ph.D.

Position: Acting Director, Center for Economic and Policy Studies; Regional Economist

Institution: Weldon Cooper Center for Public Service, University of Virginia

Discipline: Input-Output Economics; Environmental Economics

DC Research Focus: Lead author of the 2026 Great Lakes data center report; co-production framework for infrastructure resilience in Loudoun County ('Living with Data Centers' project); methodology for predicting short- and long-term data center impacts

Contact & Links:

Institutional Profile: <https://www.coopercenter.org/team/joao-ferreira>

UVA Environmental Inst.: <https://environment.virginia.edu/expert/joao-pedro-da-rocha-ferreira>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=en&user=vEzRcbAAAAAJ>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/joaoprferreira/>

Key Publications / Reports:

Economic, Fiscal and Energy-related Impacts of Data Centers in the Great Lakes Region (2026). Weldon Cooper / Joyce Foundation

<https://www.coopercenter.org/research/GLDC>

Living with Data Centers: Co-Producing a Framework for Climate Resilience. UVA Environmental Institute

<https://environment.virginia.edu/data-centers-Northern-Va>

William (Bill) Shobe, Ph.D., J.D.

Position: Research Professor Emeritus of Public Policy (*title updated June 2026*)

Institution: Weldon Cooper Center / Frank Batten School, University of Virginia

Discipline: Environmental Economics; Energy Policy; Emissions Market Design

DC Research Focus: Virginia electricity demand forecasting showing data center load will surpass residential use; JLARC-commissioned study on data center economic impacts; co-author of the 2026 Great Lakes data center report; energy transition modeling; RGGI carbon market design

Contact & Links:

Batten School Profile: <https://batten.virginia.edu/people/william-shobe/>

Weldon Cooper Profile: <https://www.coopercenter.org/team/william-shobe>

Key Publications / Reports:

Virginia Energy Demand Forecast (Energy Transition Initiative). Weldon Cooper Center

<https://www.coopercenter.org/research>

Data Centers in Virginia (JLARC-commissioned study) (2024). JLARC

<https://jlarc.virginia.gov/landing-2024-data-centers-in-virginia.asp>

Terry L. Clower, Ph.D. (*new in v3.0*)

Position: Director, Center for Regional Analysis; Northern Virginia Chair and Professor of Public Policy

Institution: George Mason University, Schar School of Policy and Government

Discipline: Regional Economics; Housing Markets

DC Research Focus: Co-author of the first systematic Virginia study of data center proximity and residential property values, analyzing 2023 home sales across Northern Virginia against data center locations; the study found sale prices were higher, not lower, near data centers — cited series-wide as the principal empirical counterweight to property-value impact claims

Contact & Links:

CRA Team Page: <https://cra.gmu.edu/about/team/faculty/>

Key Publications / Reports:

Data Centers and 2023 Home Sales in Northern Virginia (August 2025). GMU Center for Regional Analysis (with Keith Waters)

https://cra.gmu.edu/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/NoVa_DataCenters.pdf

Keith Waters, Ph.D. (*new in v3.0*)

Position: Assistant Director, Stephen S. Fuller Institute; Research Faculty, Center for Regional Analysis

Institution: George Mason University, Schar School of Policy and Government

Discipline: Regional Economics; Demographics

DC Research Focus: Co-author of the GMU home-sales study (above); regional economic indicators for the Washington metro area under data center buildout

Contact & Links:

CRA Team Page: <https://cra.gmu.edu/about/team/>

Fuller Institute: <https://fullerinstitute.gmu.edu/about/>

Key Publications / Reports:

Data Centers and 2023 Home Sales in Northern Virginia (August 2025). GMU CRA (with Terry Clower)
https://cra.gmu.edu/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/NoVa_DataCenters.pdf

Mangum Economics (*new in v3.0 — organizational entry*)

Glen Allen, Virginia consultancy (CEO: A. Fletcher Mangum, Ph.D.) that has produced NVTTC's biennial data center economic impact reports since 2015, including the March 2026 sixth biennial edition (\$40 billion statewide impact, 112,000+ jobs). The 2026 NVTTC report is a Mangum product, not a Weldon Cooper product — a distinction that matters when weighing it against the JLARC and Cooper Center literature, since the NVTTC series is industry-commissioned.

<https://www.mangumeconomics.com/>

2. Utility Regulation, Energy Law & Ratepayer Advocacy

Mark Christie

Position: Founding Director, Center for Energy Law & Policy; Visiting Professor of the Practice and Lowance Fellow (*updated June 2026 — left FERC August 2025; FERC Commissioner January 2021–August 2025, Chairman for his final seven months*)

Institution: William & Mary Law School

Discipline: Energy Law; Wholesale Electricity Markets; Grid Reliability

DC Research Focus: Wholesale electricity market structures insufficient for data center demand; co-location regulation (FERC December 2025 order on PJM); cost-allocation mechanisms for new dispatchable capacity; argued the reliability crisis is 'no longer over the horizon'; testified before House Energy & Commerce Subcommittee May 13, 2026; the new W&M center's stated focus includes data center demand

Contact & Links:

Center Faculty & Staff: <https://law.wm.edu/academics/intellecualife/researchcenters/energy-law-policy/faculty-staff/>

Appointment Announcement: <https://law.wm.edu/news/stories/2025/energy-leader-mark-christie-to-direct-william-mary-laws-new-center-for-energy-law-policy.php>

Will Cleveland

Position: Principal, Lighthouse Policy & Law, PLC (*updated June 2026 — left SELC; served as Transition Chief of Staff to Virginia Attorney General-elect Jay Jones, November 2025–January 2026; serves on Virginia's Clean Energy Advisory Board*)

Institution: Lighthouse Policy & Law, PLC

Discipline: Energy Law; Utility Regulation; Ratepayer Advocacy

DC Research Focus: Ratepayer advocacy in Dominion Energy rate cases; documented utility over-earning (\$1.2B since 2015); zero-carbon grid transitions; SCC proceeding testimony challenging data center cost allocation to residential ratepayers

Contact & Links: [general channel only]

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/will-cleveland-20871a3a/>

Clean Energy Advisory Board: <https://energy.virginia.gov/renewable-energy/CEAB.shtml>

Dalia Patino-Echeverri, Ph.D.

Position: Gendell Family Associate Professor

Institution: Duke University, Nicholas School of the Environment

Discipline: Energy System Policy Design; Uncertainty Analysis

DC Research Focus: Leads the ALIGN Initiative (Advanced Load Integration for Grid Needs) on data-center load growth; co-author of Duke's widely cited 'Rethinking Load Growth' analysis on grid flexibility for large loads; EPRI DCFlex participant

Contact & Links:

Duke Profile: <https://scholars.duke.edu/person/dalia.patino>

Key Publications / Reports:

Rethinking Load Growth: Assessing the Potential for Integration of Large Flexible Loads in US Power Systems. Nicholas Institute, Duke University

<https://nicholasinstitute.duke.edu/sites/default/files/publications/rethinking-load-growth.pdf>

Data Centers and Generation Capacity over the Next Decade: Potential Benefits of Flexibility. Nicholas Institute
<https://nicholasinstitute.duke.edu/sites/default/files/publications/data-centers-generation-capacity-over-next-decade.pdf>

Allison Clements

Position: Principal, 804 Advisory; Partner, ASG; former FERC Commissioner (2020–2024) (*affiliation updated June 2026*)

Institution: 804 Advisory / ASG

Discipline: Energy Regulation; Grid Reliability

DC Research Focus: Data center operational flexibility as a grid resource; contractual and regulatory enablers for flexible data center loads; 2026 commentary on DOE's large-load flexibility framework

Contact & Links:

Kleinman Center Bio: <https://kleinmanenergy.upenn.edu/people/allison-clements/>

Recent Commentary: <https://www.utilitydive.com/news/data-center-flexibility-doe-large-load-ferc/804797/>

Rachel James (*new in v3.0*)

Position: Staff Attorney, Virginia office

Institution: Southern Environmental Law Center (SELC)

Discipline: Energy Law; Environmental Justice

DC Research Focus: Lead SELC attorney on the Chesterfield Energy Reliability Center (CERC) litigation — the 944 MW gas peaker approved November 2025 to serve data-center-driven load, now on appeal at the Supreme Court of Virginia on behalf of the Chesterfield NAACP, Appalachian Voices, and Mothers Out Front; practices before the Virginia SCC; former Hawai'i PUC staff attorney

Contact & Links:

SELC Staff Profile: <https://www.selc.org/staff/rachel-james/>

Harvard Environmental & Energy Law Program (EELP)

Extracting Profits from the Public: How Utility Ratepayers Are Paying for Big Tech's Power (2025). Key report documenting wealth transfers from captive residential consumers to large tech entities through utility rate structures.

<http://eelp.law.harvard.edu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Harvard-ELI-Extracting-Profits-from-the-Public.pdf>

IEEFA (Institute for Energy Economics and Financial Analysis)

Dennis Wamsted and Seth Feaster: PJM capacity price analysis showing data centers responsible for ~63% of the price surge (\$28.92 to \$329.17/MW-day); 2026 work includes the gas power plant stampede case study and PJM private-equity risk analysis. Cathy Kunkel (Energy Consultant): Southeastern gas pipeline buildouts driven by data center demand. Cathy Kunkel is also a consultant to the Emory/Sloan project. All three confirmed at IEEFA June 2026.

<https://ieefa.org/people/dennis-wamsted>
<https://ieefa.org/people/seth-feaster>
<https://ieefa.org/people/cathy-kunkel>

3. Water Resources & Environmental Engineering

Landon Marston, Ph.D., P.E.

Position: Associate Professor, Civil and Environmental Engineering

Institution: Virginia Tech

Discipline: Water Resources Engineering; Human-Water Systems; Food-Energy-Water Nexus

DC Research Focus: First-ever spatially detailed calculation of carbon and water footprint of U.S. data centers; localized water stress from hyperscale facilities ('giant soda straw' effect); one-fifth of U.S. data centers draw from moderately to highly stressed watersheds; 2026 work on the power-water trade-off in data center resource allocation

Contact & Links:

VT Faculty Profile: <https://cee.vt.edu/people/faculty/lmarston.html>

Lab Website: <http://marstonresearchgroup.com/>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=Q7BS0vEAAAAJ&hl=en>

Office: 220C Patton Hall, Blacksburg, VA 24061

Key Publications / Reports:

The environmental footprint of data centers in the United States (Siddik, Shehabi & Marston) (2021). Environmental Research Letters

<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abfba1>

Power-water trade-offs in data center resource allocation (2026). Virginia Tech

<https://news.vt.edu/articles/2026/04/power-water-data-centers-resource-allocation.html>

United States Water Withdrawals Database (188,857 unique water users) (2026). Virginia Tech

<https://news.vt.edu/articles/2026/01/eng-cee-water-database.html>

Shaolei Ren, Ph.D.

Position: Associate Professor, Electrical and Computer Engineering

Institution: University of California, Riverside

Discipline: Sustainable AI; Water-Energy Nexus; Responsible Computing

DC Research Focus: Pioneered methodology to estimate the 'secret water footprint' of AI models; calculated GPT-3 training consumed 5.4M liters; projects global AI water withdrawal could reach 4.2–6.6 billion cubic meters by 2027; 2026 work quantifies data center impacts on public water systems (\$10–58B infrastructure cost estimate, with Wierman/Caltech); advocates 'Water Capacity Neutral' / 'Pipe Neutral' approaches

Contact & Links:

Personal Website: <https://shaoleiren.github.io/>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=h7N96TUAAAAJ&hl=en>

Email: shaolei@ucr.edu

Office: Winston Chung Hall 319, Riverside, CA 92521. (951) 827-2260

Key Publications / Reports:

Making AI Less 'Thirsty': Uncovering and Addressing the Secret Water Footprint of AI Models (Li, Yang, Islam & Ren) (2025). Communications of the ACM

<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3724499>

Small Bottle, Big Pipe: Quantifying and Addressing the Impact of Data Centers on Public Water Systems (Han, Li, Wierman & Ren) (2026). arXiv

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.03271>

4. Air Quality, Public Health & Environmental Justice

Damian Pitt, Ph.D.

Position: Associate Professor of Urban Planning; Chair, Urban and Regional Studies and Planning; Associate Director of Policy and Community Engagement, Institute for Sustainable Energy and Environment (ISEE)

Institution: Virginia Commonwealth University (VCU)

Discipline: Urban & Environmental Planning; Environmental Justice

DC Research Focus: Quantifying localized air pollution from data center backup diesel generators in Northern Virginia; demonstrating cumulative emissions from 100+ facilities rival nearby power plants; correlating exposure with income and education demographics

Contact & Links:

VCU ISEE Publications: https://scholarscompass.vcu.edu/isee_pubs/

ISEE Profile: <https://isee.vcu.edu/news/newsroom/isee-news/connecting-equity-and-sustainability-damian-pitt-drives-research-to-advance-the-long-term-future-of-energy-policy.html>

Key Publications / Reports:

Localized Air Pollution Impacts from Data Centers in Northern Virginia (2026). Pitt, Suen, and Plisko. VCU ISEE https://scholarscompass.vcu.edu/isee_pubs/3/

Ivan Suen

Position: Researcher, VCU Institute for Sustainable Energy and Environment

Institution: Virginia Commonwealth University

Discipline: Environmental Science; Air Quality Modeling

DC Research Focus: Co-author of VCU data center air pollution study; GIS-based emissions modeling

Contact & Links:

Published Work: https://scholarscompass.vcu.edu/isee_pubs/3/

Ellie Plisko

Position: Researcher, VCU Institute for Sustainable Energy and Environment

Institution: Virginia Commonwealth University

Discipline: Environmental Science

DC Research Focus: Co-author of VCU data center air pollution study; demographic exposure analysis correlating emissions with socioeconomic characteristics

Contact & Links:

Published Work: https://scholarscompass.vcu.edu/isee_pubs/3/

Neha Gour, Luis E. Ortiz & Edward W. Maibach (*new in v3.0*)

Position: Research Team, George Mason University (Maibach: Distinguished University Professor, Center for Climate Change Communication)

Institution: George Mason University

Discipline: Public Health; Urban Climate; Climate Communication

DC Research Focus: Authors of the first exploratory health assessment of Virginia's data center buildout, covering noise, air pollution, and energy-cost pathways to health outcomes; the study anchored U.S. News national coverage of data center health impacts (April 2026)

Key Publications / Reports:

Health implications of the rapid rise of data centers in Virginia: an exploratory assessment (2026). *Frontiers in Climate*
<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/climate/articles/10.3389/fclim.2026.1648912/full>

5. Thermal Management & Data Center Engineering

Jiangtao Cheng, Ph.D., ASME Fellow

Position: Associate Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering

Institution: Virginia Tech

Discipline: Thermal-Fluid Sciences; Machine Learning; Spray Cooling

DC Research Focus: AI-optimized spray cooling for data center thermal management; machine learning algorithms (inspired by AlphaGo) to predict optimal droplet configurations; Leidenfrost effect research for advanced surface cooling published in *Nature Physics*

Contact & Links:

VT Faculty Profile: <https://me.vt.edu/people/faculty/cheng-jiangtao.html>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=BcaCkEoAAAAJ&hl=en>

Key Publications / Reports:

Thermohydraulic performance of spray cooling systems: a general model by machine learning (2025). *Artificial Intelligence Review* (with Zhenhua Tian)

AI analysis inspired by ancient game gives cooling clues (2025). Virginia Tech

<https://news.vt.edu/articles/2025/11/eng-me-ai-spray-cooling-cheng.html>

Jeffrey Moran, Ph.D. (with Sajad Kargar, Ph.D. student)

Position: Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering

Institution: George Mason University

Discipline: Mechanical Engineering; Building Physics

DC Research Focus: Transforming data center buildings into heat exchangers; 'free cooling' via natural convection; hybrid liquid/air data center cooling research in the Moran Research Group; GMU secured \$1.5M to launch AI data center research lab (January 2026)

Contact & Links:

GMU Profile: <https://www.gmu.edu/profiles/jmoran23>

Lab Website: <https://moranresearchgroup.org/>

GMU Lab Announcement: <https://www.gmu.edu/news/2026-01/george-mason-secures-15m-launch-cutting-edge-ai-data-center-research-lab>

6. Architecture, Design & Land Use Innovation

Ali Fard, DDes

Position: Assistant Professor of Architecture; Director, MIST_lab

Institution: University of Virginia School of Architecture

Discipline: Architecture; Technical Landscape Design; Adaptive Reuse

DC Research Focus: Reimagining data center 'Technical Landscapes' in Northern Virginia; Infrastructure Interchanges; Adaptive Reuse / 'Second Lives' for data centers after 20-year operational lifespan; SOM Foundation 2025 Research Prize for data-center-mobility research ('Through the Cloud'); book published Spring 2026

Contact & Links:

UVA Architecture Profile: <https://www.arch.virginia.edu/people/ali-fard>

Key Publications / Reports:

Grounding the Cloud: Urbanism in the Shadow of Data (2026). University of Minnesota Press — published <https://www.upress.umn.edu/9781517919610/grounding-the-cloud/>

Platforms and Palimpsests: Urban Landscapes of Data in Northern Virginia (2023). Footprint Journal <https://doi.org/10.59490/footprint.17.2.6726>

HKS Architects

Design research firm exploring mass timber superstructures for edge data centers to reduce embodied carbon and improve thermal efficiency. Published an 'AI Age Data Center Report' forecasting design trends through 2030. Shell flexibility designs accommodate evolving IT infrastructure without full structural rebuilds.

<https://www.hksinc.com/>

Multi-Story and Vertical Design Innovations

In high-barrier Northern Virginia markets (land prices up to \$1M/acre), developers are moving from single-story footprints to 2-to-4 story designs to optimize Floor Area Ratio. The CloudHQ LC-2 project in Ashburn used precast double tees to support heavy mechanical systems and generators on a rooftop penthouse, enabling a 489,000 sq ft building to handle 96 MW critical load on a constrained site.

Urban Data Centers and Symbiotic Integration

Emerging design concepts propose integrating servers with public squares, urban parks, and commercial markets, with data centers acting as urban landmarks providing public heat utility services. Agri-circular models explore co-locating data centers with dairy farms (manure digesters for energy, waste heat for greenhouses) and agrivoltaic arrays (solar fields doubling as insect and pollinator habitats).

7. Critical Data Center Studies & Science and Technology Studies

Dustin Edwards

Position: Associate Professor of Rhetoric and Writing Studies; Director, University Writing Center

Institution: San Diego State University

Discipline: Rhetoric; Technical Communication; Digital Damage Studies

DC Research Focus: Coined 'digital damage'; argues hyperscale AI construction represents extractive capitalist logic where land, water, and minerals are sacrificed for a tech-dominant future; co-originated the field of critical data center studies; new book on data centers forthcoming from University of Alabama Press

Contact & Links:

Personal Website: <https://dustinwedwards.com/>

Key Publications / Reports:

Enduring Digital Damage: Rhetorical Reckonings for Planetary Survival (2025). Book https://books.google.com/books/about/Enduring_Digital_Damage.html?id=OSyPEQAAQBAJ

The Making of Critical Data Center Studies (2024). Convergence (with Zane Cooper) <https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565231224157>

Zane Griffin Talley Cooper

Position: Assistant Professor

Institution: St. Lawrence University

Discipline: Critical Infrastructure Studies; Digital Energetics

DC Research Focus: Arctic energy-water nexus and data centers; connects data centers to raw resource extraction regimes; co-originated critical data center studies; co-launching the Climate, Technology, & Justice research program at Data & Society (with Tamara Kneese)

Contact & Links:

Faculty Profile: <https://www.stlawu.edu/people/zane-griffin-talley-cooper>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=wFGzn8IAAAAJ&hl=en>

Key Publications / Reports:

The Making of Critical Data Center Studies (with Edwards & Hogan) (2024). Convergence

<https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565231224157>

Digital Energetics (with Pasek, Lin & Kinder) (2023). University of Minnesota Press

Of dog kennels, magnets, and hard drives: Dealing with Big Data peripheries (2021). Big Data & Society

<https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517211015430>

Mel Hogan

Position: Associate Professor, Department of Film and Media; Director, Environmental Media Lab (*institution updated June 2026 — moved from University of Calgary*)

Institution: Queen's University (Kingston, Ontario)

Discipline: Environmental Media; Critical Data Center Art

DC Research Focus: Environmental media in the cloud; creative interventions narrating 'suspended failure' of data center development projects; data center materiality; hosts The Data Fix podcast

Contact & Links:

Queen's Profile: <https://www.queensu.ca/filmandmedia/people-search/mel-hogan>

Environmental Media Lab: <https://environmentalmedialab.com/eml-team>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=Y7y8VbAAAAAJ>

Miriam Posner

Position: Associate Professor

Institution: UCLA, Information Studies / Digital Humanities

Discipline: Information Studies; Supply Chain Opacity

DC Research Focus: Supply chain management software and opacity of mineral sourcing in AI hardware; book *Seeing Like a Supply Chain* (Yale University Press) due fall 2026

Contact & Links:

UCLA Profile: <https://seis.ucla.edu/faculty-and-research/faculty-directory/miriam-posner>

Ana Valdivia

Position: Departmental Research Lecturer in AI, Government & Policy (*title updated June 2026*)

Institution: Oxford Internet Institute

Discipline: Ethnography; AI Supply Chains

DC Research Focus: Leads project on data centers transforming territories in Chile and Mexico; embodied and environmental repercussions of data center hardware production

Contact & Links:

Oxford Profile: <https://www.oii.ox.ac.uk/people/profiles/ana-valdivia/>

8. Labor Economics & Employment Effects

Michael J. Hicks, Ph.D.

Position: Director, Center for Business and Economic Research (CBER); Professor

Institution: Ball State University

Discipline: Labor Economics; Regional Economic Development

DC Research Focus: Causal studies (Texas, Indiana) showing data centers have 'almost no local economic effects' beyond construction peaks; statewide tax incentives frequently 'unjustifiable'; March 2026 syndicated column on the data center backlash

Contact & Links:

BSU Profile: <https://www.bsu.edu/academics/centersandinstitutes/cber/about-us/staff/hicksmichael> (URL updated June 2026)

CBER Commentary: <https://commentaries.cberdata.org/1335/a-data-center-study>

Substack: <https://michaeljhicks.substack.com/p/data-centers-and-local-job-creation>

Key Publications / Reports:

Data Centers and Local Job Creation (causal estimates from Texas) (2025). CBER / Substack
<https://michaeljhicks.substack.com/p/data-centers-and-local-job-creation>

Ben Green, Ph.D.

Position: Assistant Professor, School of Information (courtesy appointment, Ford School of Public Policy)
(affiliation updated June 2026)

Institution: University of Michigan

Discipline: Public Policy; Government Algorithms; Community Impacts

DC Research Focus: Authored 'What Happens When Data Centers Come to Town?' documenting environmental/economic pressures on host communities; argues data centers operate more like infrastructure projects than job-creating businesses; documents NDA-shielded negotiations between tech companies and local governments

Contact & Links:

U-M Profile: <https://www.si.umich.edu/people/ben-green>

Ford School: <https://fordschool.umich.edu/faculty/ben-green>

Email: bzgreen@umich.edu

Key Publications / Reports:

What Happens When Data Centers Come to Town? (2025). UM Science, Technology & Public Policy Program
<https://stpp.fordschool.umich.edu/sites/stpp/files/2025-07/stpp-data-centers-2025.pdf>

Mark Muro

Position: Senior Fellow

Institution: Brookings Institution (Brookings Metro)

Discipline: Regional Technology Hubs; Workforce Development

DC Research Focus: Data center leverage for local prosperity; February 2026 Brookings analysis of new evidence on data center employment effects; Community Benefit Agreement frameworks

Contact & Links:

Brookings Profile: <https://www.brookings.edu/people/mark-muro/>

Key Publications / Reports:

New evidence on data center employment effects (February 2026). Brookings

Turning the Data Center Boom into Long-Term, Local Prosperity. Brookings

<https://www.brookings.edu/articles/turning-the-data-center-boom-into-long-term-local-prosperity/>

The Local Implications of Data Centers for Rural Communities in the US. Brookings

<https://www.brookings.edu/articles/local-implications-data-centers-rural-communities-us/>

Nicol Turner Lee

Position: Senior Fellow, Governance Studies; Director, Center for Technology Innovation

Institution: Brookings Institution

Discipline: Digital Equity; Community Benefit Agreements

DC Research Focus: CBA frameworks for data centers including noise/light standards, \$20+/hour wage floors, community equity endowments; AI's impact on rural society; runs the AI Equity Lab

Contact & Links:

Brookings Profile: <https://www.brookings.edu/people/nicol-turner-lee/>

9. Computing, Sustainability & Socioeconomic Impacts

Wacuka Ngata, Noman Bashir, et al.

Position: Research Team (MIT / UMass Amherst). Faculty PI: Elsa Olivetti. (*Note, June 2026: Bashir has left MIT and is now an Applied Scientist at Amazon Web Services working on data-center sustainability — factor this affiliation into any outreach.*)

Institution: Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Discipline: Sustainable Computing; Socio-Environmental Studies

DC Research Focus: Mixed-methods study of community-level impacts in Northern Virginia's 'Data Center Valley'; quantitative data on resource strain, grid stress, economic costs, noise pollution, air pollution; qualitative community perspectives on distributional justice

Contact & Links:

Noman Bashir Website: <https://noman-bashir.github.io/>

ArXiv Paper: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.03367>

Key Publications / Reports:

The Cloud Next Door: Investigating the Environmental and Socioeconomic Strain of Datacenters on Local Communities (2025). ACM COMPASS '25

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.03367>

Reem Kseibati

Position: Researcher, MIT Center for Real Estate

Institution: Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Discipline: Circular Economy; Real Estate

DC Research Focus: Circular economy frameworks for data centers; lifecycle analysis of data center materials and infrastructure

Contact & Links:

MIT DSpace: <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/158889>

Key Publications / Reports:

Towards a Circular Economy for Data Centers (2025). MIT CRE

<https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/158889>

10. Southern U.S. Researchers Outside Virginia

10a. Georgia

Ahmed Saeed

Position: Assistant Professor, School of Computer Science

Institution: Georgia Institute of Technology

Discipline: Computer Science; Data Center Optimization

DC Research Focus: 'Hidden footprint' of data centers; AI training workloads pressuring local infrastructure and water consumption; workload optimization for 4–12% power savings

Contact & Links:

Personal/Faculty Page: <https://faculty.cc.gatech.edu/~amsmti3/> (URL updated June 2026)

Google Scholar: https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=n_ZpC0QAAAAJ&hl=en

Personal Website: <https://saeed.github.io/>

Key Publications / Reports:

The Future of Data Center Development in Georgia: Overview and Policy Exploration (2026). Georgia Tech Policy Brief (with Hester)

https://saeed.github.io/files/Policy_Brief_on_Data_Center_Development_in%20Georgia.pdf

Tony Harding

Position: Assistant Professor

Institution: Georgia Tech, Jimmy and Rosalynn Carter School of Public Policy

Discipline: Environmental & Energy Economics

DC Research Focus: Economic modeling of data center clustering effects on urban housing markets and residential electricity prices; water stress from competition with farmers and residential users

Contact & Links:

GT Profile: <https://spp.gatech.edu/people/person/tony-harding> (URL updated June 2026)

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=Ub9Ei6YAAAAJ&hl=en>

Key Publications / Reports:

Watts and bots: The energy implications of AI adoption (with Moreno-Cruz) (2025). Environmental Research Letters

<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ae0e3b>

Marilyn Brown

Position: Regents' and Brook Byers Professor of Sustainable Systems

Institution: Georgia Tech, School of Public Policy

Discipline: Sustainable Energy Systems

DC Research Focus: Multi-decade sustainable energy strategy for Georgia under data center demand growth

Contact & Links:

GT Profile: <https://spp.gatech.edu/people/person/marilyn-a-brown> (URL updated June 2026)

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=L-vD1pUAAAAJ&hl=en>

EPIcenter: <https://epicenter.energy.gatech.edu/>

Daniel Molzahn

Position: Associate Professor

Institution: Georgia Tech, ECE

Discipline: Power Systems; Grid Modernization

DC Research Focus: Grid modernization under high data center load; developer of 'Current Crisis' educational game; featured in Georgia Tech's 'Understanding the Data Center Building Boom' (February 2026)

Contact & Links:

GT ECE Profile: <https://ece.gatech.edu/directory/daniel-molzahn>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=S9A7O2kAAAAJ&hl=en>

10b. Tennessee

Gabe Schwartzman

Position: Assistant Professor of Geography & Sustainability (Sloan Co-PI)

Institution: University of Tennessee, Knoxville

Discipline: Geography; Energy Transition

DC Research Focus: Energy transition, rural development, and fossil fuel infrastructure buildout for data centers; TVA's proposed gas plants and pipelines in response to data center demand; co-PI on the \$1M Sloan Foundation grant (with Emory) for the three-year study of data center impacts on rural communities in Tennessee, Georgia, and Virginia

Contact & Links:

UTK Geography: <https://geography.utk.edu/people/gabe-schwartzman/>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/scientific-contributions/Gabe-Schwartzman-2292226102>

Key Publications / Reports:

Power and Just Transition: the Struggle for a Post-Coal Future in an Appalachian Valley (2026). University of Illinois Press

<https://www.press.uillinois.edu/books/?id=c046933>

Afterlives of coal: land and transition dynamics in Central Appalachia (with Shade et al.) (2025). Environmental Research: Energy

<https://doi.org/10.1088/2753-3751/adb1ea>

Nikki Luke

Position: Assistant Professor (Sloan Consultant); Member, DOE 21st Century Energy Workforce Advisory Board (appointed February 2025)

Institution: University of Tennessee, Knoxville

Discipline: Human Geography; Energy & Labor Politics

DC Research Focus: Energy and labor politics related to Southern data center development; distributional justice in utility service territories

Contact & Links:

UTK Geography: <https://geography.utk.edu/people/nikki-luke/>

Google Scholar: <https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=aVdyk3AAAAAJ&hl=en>

Key Publications / Reports:

Data centers told to pitch in as storms and cold weather boost power demand (with Harrison) (2026). The Conversation

<https://theconversation.com/data-centers-told-to-pitch-in-as-storms-and-cold-weather-boost-power-demand-222456>

Not Just Another Utility: The TVA and Public Power in the Energy Transition (with Welton & Phillips) (2025). Iowa Law Review

10c. North Carolina & South Carolina

Sasha Weintraub

Position: Executive Vice President and Chief Customer Officer (*title updated June 2026; the NC State lecturer line in v2.1 could not be re-verified and has been dropped*)

Institution: Duke Energy

Discipline: Utility Strategy; Rate Design

DC Research Focus: Grid strategies and customer pricing models for integrating large AI data center loads

Contact & Links:

Duke Energy Leadership: <https://www.duke-energy.com/our-company/about-us/leadership/sasha-weintraub>
Jill Gemmill

Position: Associate Vice President, Research Computing & Data; Research Professor, ECE

Institution: Clemson University

Discipline: High-Performance Computing

DC Research Focus: Manages 'Palmetto' HPC cluster; high-performance networking and storage solutions serving as institutional resource for regional data center research

Contact & Links:

Clemson Profile: <https://ccit.clemson.edu/research/researcher-profiles/jill-gemmill/>

10d. Texas

Brian A. Korgel

Position: Director, Energy Institute; Rashid Engineering Regents Chair

Institution: University of Texas at Austin

Discipline: Energy Systems; Large Load Integration

DC Research Focus: Lead for the UT Large Load Symposium; grid reliability solutions for industrial-scale data center growth in ERCOT

Contact & Links:

UT Energy Institute: <https://energy.utexas.edu/about/people/brian-korgel> (*URL updated June 2026*)

Xin Chen

Position: Assistant Professor, ECE; Co-Director, Consortium on AI and Large Flexible Load (CALL)

Institution: Texas A&M University

Discipline: Power Systems Modeling

DC Research Focus: Dynamic modeling of AI data centers and their interactions with the power grid; ERCOT partnership on open-source EMT models for large load behavior; NSF CAREER Award recipient

Contact & Links:

TAMU Profile: <https://engineering.tamu.edu/electrical/profiles/chen-xin.html> (*URL updated June 2026*)

Tom Overbye

Position: Professor and Director, TEES Smart Grid Center; O'Donnell Foundation Chair III

Institution: Texas A&M University

Discipline: Power Systems; Grid Simulation

DC Research Focus: Control center facilities emulating end-to-end grid systems under large data center loads; ERCOT partnership on grid stability research

Contact & Links:

Smart Grid Center: <https://smartgridcenter.tamu.edu/>

ERCOT Partnership: <https://engineering.tamu.edu/news/2025/11/ercot-and-tees-partner-on-grid-stability.html>

Kenneth Medlock

Position: Senior Director, Center for Energy Studies; Baker Fellow in Energy and Resource Economics

Institution: Rice University, Baker Institute

Discipline: Energy Transition; Stakeholder Management

DC Research Focus: Energy-HPC-AI integration; flagged by Rice as expert on the Texas data center boom's energy, water, and political tensions (2026); hosts annual Energy HPC & AI Conference

Contact & Links:

Baker Institute: <https://www.bakerinstitute.org/expert/kenneth-b-medlock-iii>

11. Land Use Advocacy & Policy Organizations

Julie Bolthouse, M.S., M.U.R.P.

Position: Director of Land Use

Institution: Piedmont Environmental Council (PEC)

Discipline: Land Use Planning; Conservation; Environmental Policy

DC Research Focus: Leading advocacy voice on Virginia data center land use, transmission infrastructure, and eminent domain; co-organizes the Virginia Data Center Reform Coalition; documentation of transmission proposals, diesel generator impacts, ratepayer cost allocation, and cumulative environmental impacts across the Piedmont region

Contact & Links:

Email: jbolthouse@pecva.org

PEC Staff Page: <https://www.pecva.org/about/staff-and-board-listing/pec-staff/bolthouse-julie/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/julie-bolthouse-23772353/>

Key Publications / Reports:

Power Surge: Data Center Boom Leads to Expansive Transmission Proposals (2023). PEC

<https://www.pecva.org/resources/publications/piedmont-view/power-surge-data-center-boom-leads-to-expansive-transmission-proposals/>

Will 2026 be the year Virginia stops reckless data center development? (2026). Daily Progress op-ed

https://dailyprogress.com/opinion/column/article_ecd5fad9-ba1a-50f2-be0c-59e2e7bc1921.html

Nate Benforado

Position: Senior Attorney (*title and URL updated June 2026*)

Institution: Southern Environmental Law Center (SELC)

Discipline: Environmental Law; Energy Regulation

DC Research Focus: Legal advocacy on data center energy and environmental impacts in Virginia; utility regulatory proceedings; quoted on the SCC's 2025–26 Dominion rate order requiring data centers to 'pay fair share' and on 2026 General Assembly data center legislation

Contact & Links:

SELC Staff Profile: <https://www.selc.org/staff/nate-benforado/>

12. Regional Initiatives & Projects

Project Oasis

Position: Regional Economic Development Initiative

Institution: InvestSWVA / LENOWISCO PDC / SW VA Energy R&D Authority

Discipline: Brownfield Redevelopment; Geothermal Cooling

DC Research Focus: Blueprint for data center campuses on previously-mined brownfield properties in Wise County; 51-degree underground mine pool water for geothermal cooling (est. \$1M+ annual savings for 36 MW facility); clean energy generation on reclaimed coal lands

Contact & Links:

Project Website: <https://www.energydeltalab.org/project-oasis>

Living with Data Centers Project

Position: Collaborative Research Project

Institution: UVA Environmental Institute / Weldon Cooper Center

Discipline: Environmental Resilience; Community Engagement

DC Research Focus: Co-producing a framework for climate, community, and infrastructure resilience in Loudoun County, integrating community perspectives with technical analyses of grid reliability

Contact & Links:

Project Page: <https://environment.virginia.edu/data-centers-Northern-Va>

13. Investigative Journalists & Research-Grade Reporting

These organizations produce original, data-driven investigative coverage of data center impacts. They are functional primary sources for academic research. For Virginia local and regional press by coverage area, see Part IV (new in v3.0).

Latitude Media — Maeve Allsup (confirmed June 2026). Reality checks on flexible data center claims and compute-power projections.

<https://www.latitudemedia.com/authors/maeve-allsup/>

IEEFA — Dennis Wamsted / Seth Feaster. PJM capacity price analysis; infrastructure overbuild risk. Cathy Kunkel on Southeastern gas pipeline buildouts.

<https://ieefa.org/resources/projected-data-center-growth-spurs-pjm-capacity-prices-factor-10>

Inside Climate News — Charlie Paullin, formerly the Virginia Mercury's energy reporter (departed end of 2024), continues Virginia data center and energy coverage from Richmond.

<https://insideclimatenews.org/>

EESI (Environmental and Energy Study Institute) — Data center power demands, fossil fuel revival, and health impacts.

<https://www.eesi.org/articles/view/data-center-power-demands-are-contributing-to-higher-energy-bills>

RMI (Rocky Mountain Institute) — Fast, flexible solutions for data centers; batch processing analysis showing potential 50% energy demand reduction.

<https://rmi.org/fast-flexible-solutions-for-data-centers/>

LBNL (Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory) — Large Load Literature Review; comprehensive technical review of data center grid integration research.

https://eta-publications.lbl.gov/sites/default/files/2025-10/lbnl_lllreview_sept_update_2025_1.pdf

PART II: VIRGINIA INDUSTRY CONTACTS

This section provides named contacts at trade associations, hyperscale operators, colocation providers and campus developers, utilities and cooperatives, economic development authorities, the supply chain, and

advocacy coalitions operating in Virginia. Contact details are drawn from the organizations' current websites, corporate directories, VPAP lobbying registrations, and published press materials, re-verified June 2026.

14. Trade Associations

Data Center Coalition (DCC)

Primary membership association for the sector. Advocacy pillars: public policy, energy/sustainability, workforce development, stakeholder outreach. Active in the 2026 General Assembly session.

Josh Levi, President & CEO (*confirmed June 2026; testified before Congress September 2025*). **Nicole Riley**, Director of Virginia Government Affairs (*confirmed June 2026; registered Virginia lobbyist*).

Office: 525-K E. Market St, Leesburg. (703) 946-0314 [not re-verified June 2026]

Staff page: <https://www.datacentercoalition.org/staff>

Membership: membership@datacentercoalition.org

Northern Virginia Technology Council (NVTTC)

Maintains a dedicated Data Center and Cloud Community of Interest, the biennial data center economic impact report (see Part III), and the annual Data Center Awards (7th annual, February 18, 2026). **Jennifer Taylor**, President & CEO (*confirmed June 2026*). (703) 904-7100, jtaylor@nvtc.org [email/phone not re-verified June 2026]

<https://www.nvtc.org/communities/data-center-and-cloud/>

15. Hyperscale Operators

Amazon Web Services (AWS)

Largest individual operator in Virginia (130+ facilities). \$50B commitment to AI/supercomputing infrastructure. Louisa County: acquired 1,925 acres in central Louisa for \$72.45M (January 2026), including land north of Northeast Creek Reservoir, mostly inside the county's Technology Overlay District; withdrew an earlier conditional use permit application for up to 7.2M sq ft amid neighborhood opposition, and a third Louisa campus has since been proposed. Also expanding in King George County. Explored SMR siting at Dominion's North Anna station (2024).

Brandie Schaeffer, Sr. Manager, Land Development (*title updated June 2026; formerly Principal, Economic Development*)

The v2.1 public affairs roster (Laurie Tyson; TJ Maloney, Sam Markman, Jordan Tate, Colin Sollitt at (202) 442-2295) is carried over [not re-verified June 2026].

Google Data Centers (Virginia)

\$9B Virginia investment plan (announced August 27, 2025). Three active fronts:

Chesterfield: Bermuda Hundred campus ("Project Peanut," ~856,000 sq ft in three buildings on ~307 acres at 2700 Bermuda Hundred Road, permits filed June 2026); two additional land holdings, "Project Skye" (Upper Magnolia Green, ~880 acres) and "Project Loch" (Watkins Centre area, ~350 acres; Army Corps wetlands public notice NAO-2026-00182, May 2026). 200 MW PPA with Commonwealth Fusion Systems (June 2025).

Botetourt: Greenfield site, 312.55 acres acquired via Helio Capital LLC for \$14.06M plus \$4M for county initiatives; three data centers totaling ~921,000 sq ft, \$3B+; confirmed March 26, 2026; first building expected online 2028; water from Western Virginia Water Authority (2 MGD initially, up to 8 MGD at full buildout). Google's published locations index does not yet list Botetourt.

Community channels: northernvirginia@google.com (Virginia page, verified June 2026); loudoun-county@google.com (Loudoun page). No dedicated Chesterfield or Botetourt community page exists yet — use the Virginia page.

Virginia page: <https://datacenters.google/locations/virginia/>

Meta (formerly Facebook)

Henrico campus: \$750M initial investment (2017), now exceeding \$1.5B across 800+ acres; generative AI and dense GPU deployments. Community Action Grants program.

Kelley McCall, Regional Manager, Community & Economic Development (Eastern Region) (*confirmed June 2026*). **Rachel Peterson**, VP, Data Centers (*title standardized June 2026*).

Grants: datacenters.atmeta.com

Microsoft Corporation

Northern Virginia network plus the Southern Virginia hub: Boydton (Mecklenburg County) flagship campus since 2010, \$2B+ invested, 1.1M+ sq ft, five Boydton sites; expansion into South Hill (three sites incl. the 132-acre Hillcrest site at 210 Tunstall Road, permitted for three buildings plus substation), Chase City (two sites incl. Bailey Farm), Clarksville (Lakeside Commerce Park), and a 614-acre mitigation bank near Boydton. Served by Mecklenburg Electric Cooperative / ODEC; Dominion is building multiple new transmission lines into the county. 2,982 MW Gainesville project in Prince William County.

Community affairs channel (Southern Virginia): [general channel only] — Microsoft's published community engagement hub is the Microsoft Local Southern Virginia page; no named community affairs contact is published.

<https://local.microsoft.com/communities/americas/southern-virginia/>

The v2.1 contact roster (Kathryn Stack, Burson; Laura Pollitt, Mecklenburg project lead; Yazan Eid, utilities PM; media line (425) 638-7777) is carried over [not re-verified June 2026].

16. Colocation, Wholesale & Campus Developers

Equinix

Global interconnection leader; Ashburn campus among most connected points worldwide.

Rey Cheatham Banks, Head, US State & Local Public Policy & Government Affairs (*confirmed June 2026*; *chairs Loudoun Chamber data center subcommittee*). **Christopher Kimm** moved to SVP, Global Customer Care & Experience in 2023 and is no longer the Americas operations contact (*updated June 2026*).

The remaining v2.1 roster (Seth Brown, Amber Davison, Megan Haydasz, Michelle Rubis) is carried over [not re-verified June 2026].

<https://www.datacentercoalition.org/cpages/rey-banks>

QTS Data Centers

The portfolio's most consequential operator update. **Henrico:** ~1,100-acre, 17-building, ~8M sq ft expansion at White Oak Technology Park in Varina — RIC4 (478 acres, 10 buildings, 3.7M+ sq ft, under construction) and RIC5 (622 acres, up to 7 buildings, 4.1M+ sq ft; FAST-41 covered project); DEQ application for 370 diesel generators (544 total permitted with 11 cooling towers); resident pushback reported May 2026. **Prince William Digital Gateway, June 2026 posture:** the August 2025 circuit court ruling voiding the rezonings was affirmed by the Virginia Court of Appeals in March 2026; Compass Datacenters and Prince William County dropped their appeals in April 2026; QTS alone petitioned the Supreme Court of Virginia in May 2026, and the petition is pending. Emphasizes 'waterless' closed-loop cooling.

Leadership reshuffle (June 2026): **Tag Greason** is now Co-CEO of QTS (promoted March 2025; the v2.1 EVP Gov & External Affairs title is stale). **Nick Blessing** is now Chief of Staff (formerly public policy director; remains a

DCC board member). **Suntina Lee Hinton**, Senior Community Impact Manager (*confirmed*). **David McOmber**, EVP Federal Sales [not re-verified June 2026].

Media: media@qtsdatacenters.com [appears in 2024-era materials; not re-confirmed on a 2026 release — site is migrating to q.com]. Main: 877-787-3282.

<https://q.com/our-leadership/>
<https://www.qtsdatacenters.com/company/contact-us>

Tract (*new in v3.0*)

Denver-based data center land developer (founder and executive chairman: Grant van Rooyen). Virginia record: the ~430-acre, 900 MW Mountain Road Technology Park rezoning in Hanover County was denied 4–3 by the Board of Supervisors May 27–28, 2026, despite a planning commission recommendation of approval and Tract's offered \$15M water-infrastructure and \$6M conservation payments; earlier withdrew the 744-acre Branders Bridge proposal in Chesterfield (July 2025).

Erin Fosdick, Director of Entitlements (*confirmed on tract.com, June 2026; represented Tract at the final Hanover hearing*)

General: info@tract.com

<https://www.tract.com/who-we-are/>

Recurring land-use counsel: **Jeffrey P. Geiger**, Hirschler (Richmond) — represented Tract in the Hanover Mountain Road rezoning; also active on Powhatan County data center zoning. (804) 771-9557.

<https://www.hirschlerlaw.com/team-jeff-geiger>

EdgeCore Digital Infrastructure (*new in v3.0*)

Louisa: \$17B+, 1.1+ GW, up to 3.9M sq ft campus on 697 acres at Shannon Hill Regional Business Park (announced June 2025; land bought for \$42M; closed-loop air cooling) — touted by the Governor's office as a record Virginia investment. **Culpeper:** 1.4M sq ft campus, 216 MW initial critical load.

Media: Courtney Gaudet, VP Marketing & Communications, courtney.gaudet@edgecore.com (published in EdgeCore's January 2026 press release). **Sales/capacity:** capacity@edgecore.com.

<https://edgecore.com/locations/louisa-county-data-center>

<https://edgecore.com/locations/culpeper-data-centers>

CloudHQ

DC-based hyperscale developer; Culpeper campus among its Virginia holdings (see also LC-2 Ashburn in Part I §6).

Keith Harney, Chief Growth Officer (*confirmed on cloudhq.com team page, June 2026; third-party profiles carry stale COO/CFO titles*). KH@cloudhq.com [carried over from v2.1; not re-verified June 2026]. **HQ:** +1 (202) 607-2300.

<https://cloudhq.com/our-team/>

DataBank (*expanded in v3.0*)

Operates in the Culpeper Technology Zone; promotes its 'Responsible Data Center Growth' program, holding up Culpeper as a model of community-driven development (company-produced content, including 'The Economic Impact of Data Centers in Culpeper County').

Antonia Passalacqua, Public Policy Lead (*confirmed June 2026*). Contact via databank.com channels [general channel only].

<https://www.databank.com/resources/videos/building-responsible-data-center-growth/>

Peterson Companies (*new in v3.0*)

Fairfax-based developer building the 150-acre Culpeper Technology Campus (2M+ sq ft across up to 8–9 buildings near McDevitt Drive; power expected Q1 2027); also pursuing a \$1.5B Stafford County campus. [general channel only] — web form at [petersoncos.com/contact](https://www.petersoncos.com/contact).

<https://www.petersoncos.com/blog/peterson-companies-announces-2-million-sq-ft-data-center-campus-in-virginias-culpeper-county/>

WestDulles Properties (*new in v3.0*)

Reston-based developer (active since 1985) behind two contested Richmond-crescent projects: the ~230-acre Iron Horse project straddling the Ashland–Hanover line (78 acres in Hanover at 10171 E. Patrick Henry Road; before the Hanover Planning Commission May 2026) and a ~3M sq ft data center park at James River Industrial Center in Chesterfield, where its appeal of the county's conditional-use-permit determination was pending before the BZA as of June 2026.

Phone: (703) 480-5094 (published on site). [general channel only — no email published]

Counsel: **Brendan D. O'Toole**, Partner, Williams Mullen. otoole@williamsmullen.com (published on firm bio).

<https://westdullesproperties.com/>

<https://www.williamsmullen.com/people/brendan-d-otoole>

LS Power (*new in v3.0*)

New York-based power company (47+ GW portfolio) proposing a 205-acre, ~300 MW behind-the-meter data center campus at 10165 Old Ridge Road in Hanover County near Doswell; CUP filed December 2025 with an 85-ft height special exception; April 2026 site plans show four buildings with a GE Vernova LM6000 gas turbine plus on-site solar. [general channel only] — contact form at [lspower.com](https://www.lspower.com) (includes a media inquiries category); no Old Ridge Road project page exists.

<https://www.lspower.com/>

Digital Realty

34 data centers in Northern Virginia. The v2.1 [mediarelations@](mailto:mediarelations@digitalrealty.com) email could not be re-verified; use the newsroom page. [general channel only]

<https://www.digitalrealty.com/about/newsroom>

Compass Datacenters

Withdrew from the Prince William Digital Gateway (dropped its appeal April 2026). **Katy Hancock**, VP Community Relations (*confirmed June 2026*), (214) 212-1520. Cecilia Damian, lobbyist (Vectre Corp) [not re-verified June 2026].

Vantage Data Centers

\$2.25B Stafford County project. **John Stephenson**, SVP Public Policy, Global (*likely promoted from VP; confirmed at Vantage June 2026*), (202) 870-3205. Kaitlin Monaghan, kaitlin.monaghan@vantage-dc.com; Kenneth Hutcheson, lobbyist (Old Dominion PA) [not re-verified June 2026].

Other Operators

Sabey: **Tim Mirick**, President, Sabey Data Centers (since January 2025) (*confirmed June 2026*), (206) 281-8700. Lobbyist: Adisa Chinua Muse (Hunton Andrews Kurth), (804) 788-7240 [not re-verified].

Aligned: **Lisa Aussieker**, EVP Marketing (*confirmed June 2026*). communications@aligneddc.com. Ownership note: AIP/MGX/BlackRock GIP acquired all equity in Aligned (announced late 2025).

PowerHouse: PR: jsa_AREP@jsa.net [not re-verified June 2026]

Yondr: Ownership changed — DigitalBridge and La Caisse completed acquisition from Cathexis July 1, 2025; new CEO Aaron Wangenheim. Sarah Leaders could not be re-verified [general channel only]:
press@yondrgroup.com.

Iron Mountain: 142-acre Prince William campus; Henrico expansion (four data centers, 365,000 sq ft, first targeted 2027). datacenters@ironmountain.com (*confirmed June 2026 — note this is a sales channel, not community affairs*).

CyrusOne: Todd R. House, Senior Director, Global External Affairs (Falls Church) (*confirmed June 2026*), (703) 727-0650, thouse@cyrusone.com. Listening portal live: <https://www.cyrusone.com/listening-to-communities>

CoreSite: Megan Ruszkowski, VP Marketing, (720) 446-2014, press@CoreSite.com (*confirmed on 2025–2026 releases*).

STACK Infrastructure: Stafford Technology Campus (1+ GW, 500 acres, 19 buildings; first building topped out, first phase live ~2027); Manassas NVA05 (200 MW, fully funded). (*both confirmed current June 2026*)

Chirisa Technology Parks: \$2B Chesterfield investment; Meadowville (former Capital One facility) plus 1600 Digital Drive; 2026 expansion of two 100 MW buildings leased to CoreWeave; JV with American Real Estate Partners and Blue Owl Capital; DEQ air permit issued April 2026. (*new in v3.0*)

DC Blox: 65,000 sq ft facility on former Azalea Flea Market site, eastern Henrico. (*new in v3.0*) [general channel only]

17. Power, Utilities & Energy Developers

Dominion Energy (*updated in v3.0*)

Virginia's dominant utility and the central regulatory actor in the series. **GS-5 rate class:** approved November 25, 2025 (SCC Case PUR-2025-00058), effective January 1, 2027 — data center customers ≥25 MW must sign 14-year energy service agreements with minimum demand commitments (85% T&D, 60% generation) and upfront collateral. **CERC:** the 944 MW Chesterfield Energy Reliability Center gas peaker approved the same day (Case PUR-2025-00037, ~\$1.47B, target operation June 2029; Rider CERC ~\$4.88/month residential from March 2026); approval under appeal at the Supreme Court of Virginia (NAACP Chesterfield branch, Appalachian Voices, Mothers Out Front; SELC counsel). **Load forecast:** 2024 IRP projects 13,353 MW of data center load by 2038. **Media:** 24-hour line (804) 771-6115.
<https://news.dominionenergy.com/media-resources/>

Appalachian Power (APCo / AEP) (*new in v3.0 — the series' first non-Dominion investor-owned territory*)

AEP subsidiary serving ~500,000+ Virginia customers across western and southwest Virginia, including Botetourt County — the transmission provider for the Google Botetourt site (announced upgrades May 2026). One president covers the VA/WV/TN territory: **Brian Abraham**, President & COO (effective April 13, 2026, succeeding Aaron Walker).

Media: APCoNews@aep.com; George Porter (Roanoke-based), (540) 985-2968. Customer line: 1-800-956-4237.

<https://www.appalachianpower.com/company/news/media-contacts>

Mecklenburg Electric Cooperative (*new in v3.0*)

Distribution cooperative serving Mecklenburg County and surrounds, including the area around Microsoft's Boydton campus; subsidiary EMPOWER Broadband extends fiber across Southside.

Casey Logan, P.E., President & CEO (*confirmed June 2026* — *John C. Lee Jr. retired June 30, 2024*). HQ: Chase City. (800) 989-0776 [general channel].

<https://www.meckelec.org/about-us/leadership/>

Old Dominion Electric Cooperative (ODEC) (*new in v3.0*)

Generation and transmission cooperative supplying wholesale power to 11 member co-ops (including Mecklenburg EC and Rappahannock EC) across Virginia, Maryland, and Delaware — the wholesale layer behind co-op-served data center loads.

Chris Cosby, President & CEO (since February 2025). Glen Allen HQ: (804) 747-0592 [general channel].

<https://www.odec.com/our-cooperative/leadership-team/>

Rappahannock Electric Cooperative (REC) (*new in v3.0*)

One of Virginia's largest distribution co-ops (~175,000 connections, 22 counties), serving the Louisa and Culpeper corridors. CEO has been publicly vocal in 2025–26 on Virginia's surging energy demand.

John D. Hewa, President & CEO (*confirmed June 2026*). [general channel only — contact via myrec.coop]

<https://www.myrec.coop/leadership>

Western Virginia Water Authority (*new in v3.0*)

Regional water/wastewater authority (Roanoke City and County, Botetourt, Franklin) that will serve the Google Botetourt campus — and the defendant in the Roanoke Rambler's successful FOIA suit that forced disclosure of the project's water commitments (2 MGD initially, up to 8 MGD; Roanoke Circuit Court order, November 2025).

Michael (Mike) McEvoy, Executive Director, mike.mcevoy@westernvawater.org (published on official ED page). Main: (540) 853-5700; info@westernvawater.org; 601 S. Jefferson St., Suite 200, Roanoke.

<https://www.westernvawater.org/>

Commonwealth Fusion Systems (*new in v3.0*)

Building the ~400 MW ARC 'Fall Line Fusion Power Station' on ~100 acres at James River Industrial Park, Chesterfield (94 acres leased from Dominion), targeting early-2030s operation; estimated \$2.5B project. First fusion developer to apply for PJM interconnection (April 28, 2026; studies typically run 4–6 years). PPAs: Google (200 MW, June 2025 — largest corporate fusion offtake to date) and Eni (\$1B+, September 2025). \$863M Series B2 (August 2025); investors include Google and Nvidia's NVentures.

Kristen Cullen, VP of Global Policy and Public Affairs [title per LinkedIn/news profiles; not confirmed on [cfs.energy](https://www.cfs.energy) itself — flag in outreach]. **Media:** press@cfs.energy. **General:** info@cfs.energy.

<https://cfs.energy/chesterfield/overview/>

Hitachi Energy — South Boston Transformer Plant (*new in v3.0* — *supply chain*)

The series' verifiable supply-chain spillover: announced September 4, 2025, a \$457M investment to build a large power transformer manufacturing campus in South Boston (Halifax County), creating 825 jobs next to its existing ~670-worker plant (on site since 1968, ex-ABB). Aims to be the largest U.S. large-power-transformer plant by 2028 — LPTs being the critical grid component constraining data center and transmission buildout. [general channel only — corporate newsroom via [hitachienergy.com](https://www.hitachienergy.com)]

<https://www.vedp.org/press-release/2025-09/hitachi-energy-south-boston>

18. Economic Development Authorities & Regional Partnerships

Loudoun County DED

'Data Center Alley': most mature market in the state. 25M+ sq ft operational.
Buddy Rizer, Executive Director (*confirmed June 2026*). 1-800-LOUDOUN

<https://biz.loudoun.gov/staff-directory/buddy-rizer>

Prince William County

Christina Winn, Executive Director, Economic Development (*added June 2026*). (703) 792-5500, econdev@pwcgov.org. **Ricky O'Connor**, Acting Director, Development Services (*confirmed as Acting, June 2026 — predecessor Mandi Spina became county Chief Transformation Officer November 2025; recheck quarterly*), (703) 792-6930.

<https://www.pwcded.org>

Henrico County EDA (*leadership changed*)

Premier NoVA alternative; subsea cable connectivity hub; QTS White Oak expansion host.

Cari M. Tretina, Executive Director (effective January 1, 2026; former county chief of staff). **Anthony Romanello departed end of 2025** (now at consulting firm S.I.R.) — v2.1's listing of Tretina was forward-accurate. **Andrew Larsen**, Business Development, andrew@henrico.com. **Wendy Miller**, Managing Director. **Holly Zinn**, Marketing & Communications Manager. (*team confirmed on henrico.com, June 2026*)

<https://www.henrico.com/about-us/our-team>

Chesterfield County Economic Development (*new in v3.0*)

H. Garrett Hart III, Director (*confirmed June 2026 — but retiring effective January 1, 2027; successor not yet announced; recheck before fieldwork*). **Jake Elder**, Deputy Director of Development Services. Tenure brought LEGO, Google, Niagara, and Commonwealth Fusion Systems to the county; Chesterfield's \$0.24 data center equipment tax rate (2019) anchored the strategy.

<https://chesterfieldfits.com> (chesterfieldbusiness.com now redirects here)

Hanover County Economic Development (*new in v3.0*)

Brandon S. Turner, Director of Economic Development (*confirmed June 2026*). (804) 365-6464. Marketing I-95 corridor industrial sites; the county rejected Tract's Mountain Road project May 2026 while Iron Horse and LS Power Old Ridge Road applications remain in process.

<https://www.hanovervirginia.com/about-us/staff/>

Botetourt County (*new in v3.0*)

Kyle Rosner, Director of Economic Development (started October 27, 2025; formerly senior advisor on NTIA's \$42B BEAD program). **Gary Larowe**, County Administrator. The Google performance agreement commits at least \$1B investment and 50 jobs per building, caps the effective equipment tax rate at \$2.40/\$100 for twenty years per building, and gives Google control of 'all media and press relation services' concerning its involvement with the county.

<https://www.botetourtva.gov/721/Meet-the-Team>

Louisa County Economic Development (*new in v3.0*)

Andy Wade, Economic Development Director (*confirmed June 2026*). (540) 967-4581, awade@louisa.org (published on county site). Hosts the AWS acquisition acreage and EdgeCore's Shannon Hill campus. <https://www.louisacounty.gov/2689/Economic-Development>

Goochland County Economic Development (*new in v3.0*)

Nora Amos, Director of Economic Development (began January 2, 2026; formerly Town of Ashland planning director). The county's Technology Overlay District (~4,400 acres along Route 288, approved 4–1 November 2025) is in active litigation (see §19). <https://www.goochlandforbusiness.com>

Roanoke Regional Partnership (*new in v3.0*)

Regional EDO marketing the Roanoke region including Botetourt; central to the 17–18 month Google recruitment. **John Hull**, President/CEO (*title updated June 2026; also Executive Director, Western Virginia Regional Industrial Facility Authority*). (540) 343-2012 direct; info@roanoke.org; (540) 343-1550.

<https://roanoke.org/about-us/contact-us/>

Virginia's Growth Alliance (*new in v3.0*)

Regional EDO for Southside (Brunswick, Mecklenburg, Greensville, Lunenburg, Nottoway, Charlotte, Emporia) — the region hosting Microsoft's Boydton campus.

David W. Denny, Executive Director. [general channel only]

<https://vagrowth.com/vga-region/about>

Mid-Atlantic Broadband Communities Corporation (MBC) (*new in v3.0*)

South Boston-based nonprofit operating the open-access middle-mile fiber network across Southern Virginia; its network was instrumental in attracting Microsoft to Boydton.

Tad Deriso, President & CEO (*confirmed June 2026*). [general channel only]

<https://mbc-va.com/leadership/>

19. Advocacy Organizations & Community Coalitions (*new section in v3.0*)

Virginia Data Center Reform Coalition

Statewide coalition of 50+ environmental, conservation, historic preservation, and climate advocacy groups plus community representatives; coordinated by PEC (Julie Bolthouse, see Part I §11). Made data center reform a 2026 General Assembly priority; held Lobby Day February 9, 2026.

<https://www.pecva.org/region/regional-state-national-region/general-assembly/virginia-data-center-reform-coalition/>

Piedmont Environmental Council (PEC) (*updated*)

Nine-county Piedmont land-use organization and the institutional spine of Virginia data center advocacy. Active Culpeper County program tracking the Culpeper Technology Zone buildout, and ran the 'Data Centers in the Town of Orange? Protecting Our Small-Town Character' campaign — on February 17, 2026 the Orange Town Council voted unanimously to move data centers from by-right use to Special Use Permit in three districts and prohibit them in the Traditional Town Center district. Coordinates the Reform Coalition's 'Four Pillars' legislative framework.

Culpeper program: <https://www.pecva.org/our-region/culpeper-county/>

Orange campaign: <https://www.pecva.org/region/orange/data-centers-in-the-town-of-orange-protecting-our-small-town-character/>

Friends of Hanover (*new in v3.0*)

Grassroots coalition formed in response to industrial encroachment in Hanover County; led the six-month opposition campaign (petitions, rallies, 'Grow Tomatoes, Not Data Centers') that preceded the Board's 4–3 rejection of Tract's Mountain Road project May 28, 2026; held an Earth Day 2026 rally at the Hanover–Henrico line; operates alongside the 'Stop Hanover Data Centers' movement. [general channel only — no standalone website verified as of June 2026; the group organizes via Facebook and public meetings; see Henrico Citizen coverage for participant interviews]

<https://www.henricocitizen.com/the-data-centers-are-coming-but-some-hanover-and-henrico-residents-are-fighting-to-stop-them/>

Neighbors for Change (Goochland) (*new in v3.0*)

Goochland-based organization coordinating opposition to the county's Technology Overlay District; turned out 80+ speakers at the November 2025 public hearing; connects residents across county lines opposing data center development; tracks HHHunt and other proposals.

Contact: info@neighbors4change.com (published on site)

<https://neighbors4change.com/>

Goochland TOD Litigation (*new in v3.0*)

Four Goochland residents — Cynthia Haas, Peggy Knisley, Virginia H. Reed, and Gail A. Minnick — filed suit in Goochland Circuit Court (December 2025) to void the Technology Overlay District, alleging notice and zoning-law violations; counsel Phillip Strother. May 27, 2026: the court rejected the county's full 8,500-page record filing and ordered a revised submission; the county has appropriated \$250K for its defense. The plaintiffs coordinate with Neighbors for Change; no separate organizational web channel verified.

Coverage: <https://richmondbizsense.com/2026/05/27/judge-rejects-countys-full-8500-page-filing-in-goochland-tod-lawsuit/>

Southwest Virginia Data Center Transparency Alliance (*new in v3.0*)

The Botetourt opposition's organizational form, confirmed 2026: formed in response to Google's Greenfield project and prospective data center growth in the region; organizer **Ben Verschoor**; pressed the county and the Western Virginia Water Authority on water commitments (Carvins Cove) and NDA practice; protested at water authority meetings. [general channel only — no website verified as of June 2026; reachable via public meetings and regional press]

Coverage: <https://www.wdbj7.com/2026/03/31/data-center-transparency-group-responds-google-announcement/>

Coalition to Protect Prince William County

Longest-running locality-level data center opposition organization in Virginia (Elena Schlossberg); central to the Digital Gateway fight and its litigation aftermath; site active June 2026 ('Prince William County — THE model for Data Center Backlash,' May 16, 2026).

<https://protectpwc.org/>

CERC Litigants (Chesterfield)

The appellate coalition challenging the Chesterfield Energy Reliability Center: Chesterfield NAACP, Appalachian Voices, Mothers Out Front (Supreme Court of Virginia petition May 27, 2026), with CASA Inc. joining the air-permit challenge in Richmond Circuit Court. Counsel: SELC (Rachel James, see Part I §2).

PART III: KEY REPORTS & DATA SOURCES

20. Essential Reference Reports

JLARC: *Data Centers in Virginia*, Report 598 (December 9, 2024). The baseline state study: ~50 FTE per typical 250,000 sq ft facility (about half contractors); 13,353 MW additional demand by 2038; 49% projected increase in statewide electricity demand.

<https://jlarc.virginia.gov/landing-2024-data-centers-in-virginia.asp>

NVTC / Mangum Economics: *The Impact of Data Centers on Virginia's State and Local Economies*, 6th Biennial Report (March 2026). \$40B statewide impact, 112,000+ jobs, \$1.5B+ annual state tax revenue in 2025. (New in v3.0 — v2.1 cited only the 2024 edition. Note the production change: the biennial series is produced by Mangum Economics and industry-sponsored; weigh against JLARC accordingly.)

<https://www.nvtc.org/communities/data-center-and-cloud/report/>

NVTC / Weldon Cooper: *The Impact of Data Centers on Virginia's State and Local Economies* (2024) — retained for comparison.

<https://loudounpossible.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/2024-NVTC-Data-Center-Report.pdf>

GMU Center for Regional Analysis: *Data Centers and 2023 Home Sales in Northern Virginia* (August 2025). Clower & Waters. (New in v3.0 — cited series-wide.)

https://cra.gmu.edu/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/NoVa_DataCenters.pdf

Weldon Cooper / Joyce Foundation: *Economic, Fiscal and Energy-related Impacts of Data Centers in the Great Lakes Region* (2026)

<https://www.coopercenter.org/research/GLDC>

Data Center Watch: *Local Activism and the U.S. Data Center Boom* (rolling; Q2 2025 update reported \$98B in projects blocked or delayed in that quarter alone; \$162B since 2023). Tracks 140+ activist groups across 24–28 states. (New in v3.0. Provenance caution: funded by 10a Labs, which provides research to AI companies — an industry-side monitor of opposition, useful precisely because of what it counts. Its weekly briefing substack is a fieldwork-grade tipsheet.)

Reports: <https://www.datacenterwatch.org/q3-q4-2025>

Briefing substack: <https://datacenterwatch.substack.com/>

MultiState: 2026 state data center legislation tracking. Virginia: 61 bills considered in 2026, 15 sent to the governor, 46 carried to 2027; the \$1.6B/year sales tax exemption fight remains unresolved as of June 2026. (New in v3.0.)

Policy 101 guide: <https://www.multistate.us/resources/state-data-center-policy-101>

Virginia session wrap: <https://www.multistate.us/insider/2026/3/30/virginia-lawmakers-pass-15-data-center-bills-as-tax-exemption-fight-looms>

The American Prospect: *Take This Data Center and Shove It* (June 2, 2026). National survey of data center politics anchored in the Botetourt fight; reports at least 25 projects canceled nationally last year. (New in v3.0.)

<https://prospect.org/2026/06/02/jun-2026-take-this-data-center-and-shove-it/>

Harvard EELP: *Extracting Profits from the Public* (2025)

<http://eelp.law.harvard.edu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Harvard-ELI-Extracting-Profits-from-the-Public.pdf>

VCU ISEE: *Localized Air Pollution Impacts from Data Centers in Northern Virginia* (2026)

https://scholarscompass.vcu.edu/isee_pubs/3/

Frontiers in Climate: *Health implications of the rapid rise of data centers in Virginia* (2026). Gour, Ortiz & Maibach (GMU).

<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/climate/articles/10.3389/fclim.2026.1648912/full>

MIT / ACM COMPASS: *The Cloud Next Door* (2025). Ngata, Bashir, et al.

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.03367>

Nicholas Institute, Duke: *Rethinking Load Growth and Data Centers and Generation Capacity*

<https://nicholasinstitute.duke.edu/sites/default/files/publications/rethinking-load-growth.pdf>

Brookings Institution: *New evidence on data center employment effects* (February 2026); *The Local Implications of Data Centers for Rural Communities; Turning the Data Center Boom into Long-Term, Local Prosperity*

<https://www.brookings.edu/articles/local-implications-data-centers-rural-communities-us/>

IEEFA: *Projected Data Center Growth Spurs PJM Capacity Prices by Factor of 10*

<https://ieefa.org/resources/projected-data-center-growth-spurs-pjm-capacity-prices-factor-10>

Belfer Center, Harvard: *AI, Data Centers, and the U.S. Electric Grid: A Watershed Moment*

<https://www.belfercenter.org/research-analysis/ai-data-centers-us-electric-grid>

LBNL: *Large Load Literature Review* (2025)

https://eta-publications.lbl.gov/sites/default/files/2025-10/lbnl_illreview_sept_update_2025_1.pdf

RMI: *Fast, Flexible Solutions for Data Centers*

<https://rmi.org/fast-flexible-solutions-for-data-centers/>

Footprint Journal: *Platforms and Palimpsests* (2023). Ali Fard.

<https://doi.org/10.59490/footprint.17.2.6726>

MIT CRE: *Towards a Circular Economy for Data Centers* (2025). Kseibati.

<https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/158889>

21. Primary Regulatory Dockets (*new section in v3.0*)

All dockets searchable at the SCC's docket search portal: <https://scc.virginia.gov/docketsearch>

PUR-2025-00058 — Dominion GS-5 rate class / biennial review. Final order November 25, 2025; GS-5 effective January 1, 2027. The structural answer to data-center cost allocation; the primary docket for rate-design research.

PUR-2025-00037 — Chesterfield Energy Reliability Center (CERC). 944 MW gas peaker approved November 25, 2025; reconsideration denied February 12, 2026; on appeal at the Supreme Court of Virginia (petition filed May 27, 2026).

PUR-2024-00184 — Dominion 2024 Integrated Resource Plan (filed October 15, 2024; SCC final order July 15, 2025). Contains the 13,353 MW data center load forecast and the Synapse/Glick testimony finding \$22.4B in incremental transmission costs through 2038. (*Note: v3.0 corrects a case-number conflation — the 2024 IRP is PUR-2024-00184; PUR-2025-00184 is the separate 2025 IRP Update, filed October 15, 2025.*)

PUR-2025-00184 — Dominion 2025 IRP Update (filed October 15, 2025).

Related Chesterfield-area transmission dockets: PUR-2024-00179 (Meadowville 230 kV) and PUR-2025-00073 (Western Chesterfield 230 kV).

22. Tracking Sources & the Series' Own Case Studies (*new section in v3.0*)

Baxtel — commercial data center market tracking (site listings, capacity, ownership). Secondary source: useful for orientation and lead generation, not for citation without primary confirmation.

<https://baxtel.com/>

Data Center Dynamics (DCD) — trade press of record for the industry; fast and generally accurate on transactions, but industry-facing. Same secondary-source caution.

<https://www.datacenterdynamics.com/>

Emory/Sloan series case studies (published with DOIs):

Turner, T. *Henrico County Data Center Case Study*, v3.6 (2026). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20671032

Turner, T. *Hanover County Data Center Case Study*, v2.0 (2026). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20672049

Turner, T. *Goochland County Data Center Case Study*, v1.0 (2026). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20673468

Turner, T. *Botetourt County Data Center Case Study*, v1.0 (2026). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20673513

Turner, T. *Culpeper County Data Center Case Study*, v1.0 (2026). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20673530

Completed June 2026, DOIs to be added at the next directory revision once Zenodo registration is confirmed: Chesterfield v3.0, Orange County v3.0, Mecklenburg v1.0, Fredericksburg Ring v1.0, and Prince William v2.0. The Louisa and CFS/PPA studies are in progress.

PART IV: LOCAL PRESS & BEAT REPORTERS (*new in v3.0*)

The most valuable addition for October 2026 fieldwork. Outlets are organized by coverage region. Reporter names appear only where 2025–2026 bylines were verified; outlets whose data center coverage is real but byline-diffuse are listed at the newsroom level. Outlet status was checked June 2026 — two outlets on the v2.1-era planning list have folded or restructured, and one is in post-sale turmoil; each is flagged below. Local outlets fold; re-verify before each outreach wave.

Richmond Crescent (Henrico, Hanover, Chesterfield, Goochland edge)

Richmond BizSense — richmondbizsense.com — The business-of-record byline for the region’s data center land deals. **Jack Jacobs** carries the Hanover/Chesterfield/Henrico record almost single-handedly: Tract Mountain Road (February–May 2026), Iron Horse/WestDulles (May 2026), Chester BZA (June 4, 2026), Chirisa/Cartograf (January 2026), Goochland TOD litigation (May 2026), Tuckahoe Tech Park (June 11, 2026). <https://richmondbizsense.com/author/jack-jacobs/>

Henrico Citizen — henricocitizen.com — Nonprofit-supported local newsroom. **Liana Hardy** (government and education reporter, joined 2023): ‘Data Center Detour’ investigative feature (February 24, 2026), Centra Logistics BZA (February 26, 2026), Friends of Hanover Earth Day rally (May 12, 2026). <https://www.henricocitizen.com/author/lianahardy/>

The Richmonder — richmonder.org — Nonprofit newsroom (Report for America host). **Juliana Vandermark** (Google/Chesterfield, August 2025); **Rachel Kester** (‘Henrico became a data center hub seemingly overnight,’ April 2025). <https://www.richmonder.org/>

VPM News — vpm.org — Sustained Hanover/Goochland record: Mountain Road planning commission and final vote (April–June 2026), Goochland TOD approval (November 2025). Verified bylines: **Lyndon German** (Henrico data center revenue/housing, May 2024), **Billy Shields** (year-end review, December 2025); 2026 locality coverage continues — confirm the current byline at outreach time. <https://www.vpm.org/>

WTVR CBS 6 — wtvr.com — **Kelsey Jones** (QTS White Oak resident pushback, May 19, 2026; Henrico White Oak expansion). Also sustained Goochland TOD lawsuit coverage (April–May 2026). <https://www.wtvr.com/>

WRIC ABC 8News — wric.com — Hanover Mountain Road deferrals, Goochland TOD lawsuit proceedings (2026). Newsroom level; no single dominant byline verified.

WWBT NBC12 (12 On Your Side) — 12onyourside.com — Mountain Road community meetings (February 2026), Chesterfield BZA (June 2026). Newsroom level.

Richmond Times-Dispatch — richmond.com — Lee Enterprises daily. **Thad Green** (Chesterfield rezoning and ZOMod, 2025).

Axios Richmond — axios.com/local/richmond — Newsletter format; quick-turn items on federal permits and land deals (Project Loch wetlands notice, May 2026).

Statewide

Virginia Mercury — virginiamercury.com — The statewide policy record. **Shannon Heckt** now carries the energy/data center beat (GS-5 and cost-shift bills, April 2026; tax-exemption budget fight, February–June 2026). Note: **Charlie Pullin**, who built the Mercury’s data center archive, departed at the end of 2024 and continues Virginia coverage at Inside Climate News. <https://virginiamercury.com/>

Cardinal News — cardinalnews.org — Nonprofit covering Southwest and Southside Virginia; the deepest bench on Botetourt. **Samantha Verrelli** (Google Botetourt groundbreaking and explainers, March–April 2026), **Matt Busse** (business: APCo upgrades for Google, May 15, 2026; Wise County gas-powered campus, February 2026). Daily statewide headline roundups aggregate data center items. <https://cardinalnews.org/>

Virginia Business — virginiabusiness.com — Reliable transactional coverage statewide (Google Botetourt, Goochland litigation, Hart retirement). Newsroom level.

Goochland, Louisa & Orange

Engage Louisa — tammypurcell.substack.com — **Tammy Purcell**. The indispensable Louisa record: broke and tracked the AWS 1,925-acre acquisition (\$72.45M, January 2026), the withdrawn AWS CUP, the third AWS campus proposal, EdgeCore Shannon Hill, and supervisor positions. Nonpartisan local-government newsletter; functionally the county's paper of record on data centers.

The Central Virginian — Louisa weekly (1912–current), covering Louisa and Lake Anna. Active; thin staffing typical of weeklies — pair with Engage Louisa.

Goochland Gazette — Weekly (publisher: Joy Monopoli, Richmond Suburban News group). Publishing as of June 2026; byline-diffuse — pair with Richmond BizSense and Neighbors for Change's news tracking for the TOD record.

Byrd Street — byrdstreet.substack.com — **Hilary Holladay**. Independent newsletter focused on **Orange County** (placed in this cluster; v3.0 corrects the prior regional tagging): Wilderness Crossing, the Town of Orange data center fight, and Valley Link transmission line mapping.

Roanoke Valley (Botetourt)

Cardinal News — see Statewide; functionally the Roanoke Valley outlet of record on the Google project.

The Roanoke Rambler — roanokerambler.com — **Status caution (June 2026)**: founder Henri Gendreau sold the outlet to entrepreneur Ollie Howie March 30, 2026; the reporting staff (editor Todd Jackson, reporters Jeff Sturgeon and Sinclair Holian) was terminated April 10, 2026 after refusing pay-cut contracts. Verify current newsroom capacity before outreach. The Rambler's archive remains essential: its FOIA suit against the Western Virginia Water Authority (Judge Leisa Ciaffone's November 2025 disclosure order, enforced via contempt proceedings) produced the Google water-commitment record (2 → 8 MGD) and the 'Project Raspberry' courtship documents.

<https://www.roanokerambler.com/>

Roanoke Times — roanoke.com — Lee Enterprises daily; Botetourt protest and organizing coverage (2026).

WDBJ7 — wdbj7.com — Google confirmation and transparency-group responses (March 2026); data center water legislation.

WSLS 10 — wsls.com — Project document disclosures (March 2026), resident reaction.

WFXR — wfxrtv.com — Protest coverage.

WVTF / Radio IQ — wvtf.org — Public radio. **Roxy Todd** (energy/water; 'Coal, Power & Prices' series) and **Brad Kutner** (Richmond: data center commission and budget, water-disclosure law, June 2026); the February 26, 2026 NDA/water-fight piece is the single best primer on the Botetourt transparency dispute.

<https://www.wvtf.org/>

Fincastle Herald — Botetourt County weekly. [verify status before outreach — not independently confirmed June 2026]

Southside (Mecklenburg, Halifax)

SoVaNOW / The News & Record & The Mecklenburg Sun — sovanow.com — The deepest Microsoft Boydton record anywhere: campus-by-campus inventory (five Boydton sites, three South Hill, two Chase City), the mitigation bank, transmission buildout, and the 2025 'Data Center Debates' series on environmental-group pushback. Active June 2026.

<https://www.sovanow.com/>

The News Progress — thenewsprogress.com — Mecklenburg countywide weekly (Womack Publishing). **Status note**: the South Hill Enterprise — on the v2.1-era planning list — was folded into The News Progress October 11, 2023 and no longer exists as a separate newsroom; southhillenterprise.com persists as a legacy site. List The News Progress, not the Enterprise.

yourgv.com (The Gazette-Virginian) — yourgv.com — Halifax County. Carries the Hitachi Energy South Boston record (\$457M / 825 jobs announcement and performance agreement coverage).

<https://www.yourgv.com/>

Fredericksburg / NoVa Fringe (Stafford, Spotsylvania, Prince William)

The Free Lance-Star — fredericksburg.com — Lee Enterprises daily; tracking Spotsylvania's five proposed campuses (6.6M+ sq ft) and Stafford preparations.

Fredericksburg Free Press — fredericksburgfreepress.com — Nonprofit newsroom covering the region, including Spotsylvania and Stafford. (The FXBG Advance, fxbgadvance.com, is a second local digital outlet running data center analysis.)

Potomac Local News — potomaclocal.com — Dense, fast Stafford/PWC record: maintains a data centers tag page; Stafford revenue forecasts (April 2026), AccuGeek deferral blowup (May 2026), Forest Park-adjacent proposals (May 2026).

<https://www.potomaclocal.com/tag/data-centers/>

InsideNoVa — insidenova.com — Regional weekly group; sustained Digital Gateway and eastern-PWC coverage; also operates the Culpeper edition (see below). Historical bylines (Nolan Stout) not re-verified for 2026 — newsroom level.

Prince William Times — princewilliamtimes.com — Active 2026 (Forest Park data center proposals, eastern PWC expansion). Newsroom level; 2026 bylines not individually verified.

Bristow Beat — bristowbeat.com — **Stacy Shaw**, publisher/owner (*confirmed June 2026*). Western PWC: Devlin Technology Park, data center noise studies near Bristow/Gainesville schools.

<https://bristowbeat.com/>

Culpeper

Culpeper Star-Exponent — starexponent.com — Lee Enterprises daily. **Allison Brophy Champion** (Culpeper Tech Zone buildout, reclaimed-water projects; bylines through March 2026).

<https://starexponent.com/>

Culpeper Times — **Status note:** now operates as InsideNoVa's Culpeper edition rather than a standalone newsroom.

<https://www.insidenova.com/culpeper/>

Editorial Notes

Version 3.0 was compiled by mining the project's own case-study sources first — the Hanover, Henrico, Chesterfield, Goochland, Prince William, and kickoff-stage research files name nearly every entity added here — then verifying outward against the live web in June 2026. Every URL in this directory was checked June 2026; entries that could not be confirmed against an organization's current site are explicitly marked [general channel only] or [not re-verified June 2026] rather than silently carried forward. The verification pass caught five role changes among existing entries (Christie, Cleveland, Kimm, Greason, Romanello → Tretina), two institutional moves (Hogan to Queen's, Bashir to AWS), one outlet restructuring (South Hill Enterprise), one outlet in post-sale turmoil (Roanoke Rambler), and one case-number conflation (the 2024 IRP is PUR-2024-00184, not PUR-2025-00184).

Sibling directories: the Georgia directory (GA_Data_Center_Research_Directory_v4) and Tennessee directory (Tennessee_Data_Center_Research_Directory), both in the Desktop SLOAN folder, are out of scope for this revision. Both need the same treatment before October 2026 fieldwork — at minimum a still-in-role pass on every named contact and the addition of local-press sections on the Virginia Part IV model. Georgia's record has moved substantially (PSC capacity decisions, the December 2025 UGA audit); Tennessee's TVA gas buildout docket has its own 2026 litigation. Budget a directory cycle for each.

Key remaining gaps for the Emory project's Southern U.S. focus: the Carl Vinson Institute research team at UGA identified by name; Georgia PSC staff economists involved in the capacity expansion decision; TVA-affiliated grid

planning researchers; and noise/acoustics specialists studying data center operational health impacts. The directory should be treated as a living document and updated as the project progresses.

Directory v3.0 — contacts verified June 2026. Prepared by Tommy N. Turner for the Emory/Sloan Data Center Project.